

ON THE TRANSITIONS OF SECANT MODULUS OF GFRP LAMINATES FOR SHIP STRUCTURE DURING FATIGUE TEST

Sadayoshi Chiaki, Akio Sakurai

Osaka Branch, Ship Research Institute, Ministry of Transport
Amanogahara 3-5-10, Katano, Osaka 576-0034, Japan

SUMMARY: In order to know the fatigue property of GFRP laminates for ship structure, the authors performed a series of fatigue test programs on specimens from virgin GFRP laminates and on ones from bottom plates cut out from a GFRP ship used over 17 years. The virgin ones had the same lay-up pattern, but differ from one another on their thickness. The fatigue lives of GFRP laminates differ from each other, even under identical cyclic load. The cause is commonly ascribed to the differences in their fabrication processes. So to characterize the differences of each S-N plot, Secant Modulus was employed, and some remarkable characteristics were observed in their fatigue processes.

Furthermore, the tendencies in each S-N plot for tensile loaded virgin series are discussed by means of best fit lines with fiber content and thickness as parameters, and an applicability of two parameter fatigue life prediction model to this case is examined.

KEYWORDS: GFRP, Fatigue strength, Used laminated plate, Secant Modulus, Fiber content, Fatigue life prediction

INTRODUCTION

Most of small ships and fishing boats in Japan are made of glass fiber reinforced plastic consist of E-glass fiber and unsaturated polyester as matrix. Ordinary GFRP plates for ship structures have so called MR laminating pattern, where M is chopped strand mat and R denotes roving cloth. It is well known that the static strength of MR laminated plates is approximately in proportion to fiber content; see for example Kimpara [1]. Fatigue strength has been made up into an empirical formula on some short E-glass fiber reinforced SMC (Sheet Molding Compound), CSM (Chopped Strand Mat), and INJ. MLD.(Injection-Mold) by Reifsnider [2]. The fatigue resistance sensitivity B was defined in the paper and the values of each short E-glass fiber reinforced specimen showed nearly as same a value as those of continuous E-glass

fiber reinforced ones independent of the fiber content.

There has been several studies on fatigue damage accumulation or crack propagation; see for example Suzuki et al [3-4]. The crack propagation in E-glass CSM with unsaturated polyester resin was studied in the paper. The experimental results showed that the crack propagation in the substance is governed by stress intensity factor range, ΔK , and the tendency showed good agreement with traditional Paris law.

There is no previous study on fatigue property of the substantial MR laminates for ship structures focusing on the influences of thickness and fiber content. In this paper six different laminating types of MR plates were prepared for comparison and some used ones, from a bottom plate of a small boat used over 17 years, were also tested.

After being observed the tendencies in S-N plots and transition curves of secant modulus, an applicability of two parameter fatigue life prediction model to this substance is discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

MR Laminated Plates and Specimens

The specimens were square bars in the shape, and were cut out from six different laminating types of MR virgin plates and a bottom plate of a GFRP boat used over 17 years in the direction of the longitudinal fiber of roving . The average dimensions and lay up patterns are shown in Table 1, where M', M are 450, 600 [g/γ] chopped strand mat and R',R are 580, 810 [g/γ] roving cloth, respectively.

Table 1: Dimensions and lay up of specimens for both tensile and compressive tests

Series	Lay up	Thickness [mm]		Breadth [mm]		Length [mm]	
		Tensile	Compressive	Tensile	Compressive	Tensile	Compressive
Upo1	(M'+R')·3+M'	4.26	4.5	19.92	19.8	249.60	160
Upo2	(M'+R')·5+M'	6.88	6.2	19.73	19.8	249.73	160
Upo3	(M'+R')·7+M'	9.23	9.1	19.80	19.9	249.48	160
Upo4	(M+R+M)·2+M	6.23	-	19.79	-	249.89	-
Upo5	(M+R)·5+M	9.18	-	19.60	-	249.91	-
Upo6	(M+R)·7+M	11.68	-	09.85	-	249.99	-
LBL1	(M'+R)·4+M	-	8.5	-	20.0	249.99	110.1
LBT2	(M'+R)·4+M	-	8.7	-	19.97	249.99	110.2

Each virgin series was labeled Upo# which denotes orthophosphoric unsaturated polyester, and were laminated by hand lay up method. While the used series were named as LBL (Left-Bottom-Longitudinal) and LBT (Left-Bottom-Transverse). The upo1, 2, 3 and upo5, 6 series consisted of the lighter and the heavier fibers with the variation of (M'R') or (MR) repeating number, respectively. The upo4 series have a different lay up pattern in comparison with the others. The used ones had the same lay up patterns as those of the virgins.

Test Procedure

The fatigue tests were performed by a servomotor controlled testing machine with 98 [Gpa] on the capacity. The both ends of each specimen were cramped and subjected to sinusoidal cyclic loads under the conditions of 5 [Hz] in frequency and 0.01, 100 in stress ratio as tensile-tensile and compressive-compressive, respectively. All the specimens for the analysis broke at between the chucks.

PARAMETRIC COMPARISON BASED ON THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Some Comparisons by S-N plots

First, S-N plots were described for each series concerning the results of broken specimens and the best fitting lines were drawn in each plot under the assumption that S-N curves will be linear up to the conventional fatigue limit regulated to lie between 10^6 and 10^7 . Each series was added “T” as tensile and “C” as compressive at the head of the names. Table 2 shows the numerical comparison between tensile and compressive fatigue strength, which were calculated from the best fitting lines.

Table 2: Numerical comparison of fatigue strength between compressive and tensile loaded virgin series.

Series	Lay up	Thickness [mm]	S (at $N=10^3$) [MPa]	S (at $N=10^4$) [MPa]	S (at $N=10^6$) [MPa]
Cupo1	(M'+R')·3+M'	4.5	-177	-154	-106
Cupo2	(M'+R')·5+M'	6.2	-172	-151	-109
Cupo3	(M'+R')·7+M'	9.1	-177	-152	-101
Tupo1	(M'+R')·3+M'	4.3	178	148	88
Tupo2	(M'+R')·5+M'	6.9	151	125	74
Tupo3	(M'+R')·7+M'	9.2	163	132	72

It is found that compressive fatigue strength is superior to tensile one.

This tendency becomes more conspicuous as the increase of thickness and cycles to failure. For all the tensile series, each best fitting line is put together into Fig.1 with the fiber content, Vf [%], and the thickness [mm] being indicated in the parentheses on the right hand of each series name.

Fig.1 Comparison of S-N lines for all series
 Fig.2 Tensile stress range, S, versus fiber content, Vf, cycles to failure as sub parameter

It gives the influence of thickness and fiber content to tensile fatigue strength. Two notable features are observed from the tendency in Fig.1, one is that the fiber content is the dominant parameter for tensile fatigue strength in low cycles, the other is that the influence of increasing in thickness to the strength gradually appears to be an outstanding reduction of stress amplitude as the increase of the cycles to failure. From the tendencies, fiber content is regarded as the dominant parameter and thickness or scale effect is recognized as the secondary one.

So as to make the tendencies clear, the tensile stress range is shown in Fig.2 on the base of fiber content with cycles to failure as sub parameter. By observing Fig.2, it is apparent that fiber content governs tensile fatigue strength and the effect of lay up pattern seems to be negligible in this case.

Fig.3 S-N plot for Cupo1 series

Fig.6 S-N plot for CLBL1 series

Fig.4 S-N plot for Cupo2 series

Fig.7 S-N plot for CLBT2 series

Fig.5 S-N plot for Cupo3 series modulus, E_{se}

Fig.9 Schematic definition of secant

While comparing the S-N plots for virgin compressive series; Fig.3-5, to those for used compressive ones; Fig.6-7, the reductions of strengths after 17 years operation appear as notable decrease of stress amplitudes and increase of scatter. Roughly speaking, the strengths on used series are about 60 to 70 percent of those on virgins.

Table 3: Results of line fitting for Fig.3-7 by Eqn. 1, static strength, σ_0

Series	A	B	Thickness [mm]	σ_0 [Mpa]
Cupo1	2.00	0.193	4.50	124
Cupo2	1.02	0.0922	6.20	230
Cupo3	1.03	0.0981	9.10	238
CLBL1	1.35	0.118	8.50	101
CLBT2	1.33	0.130	8.70	102

Table 3 shows the values of fatigue sensitivity B for the concerning ones. It is defined by

$$\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_0 = A - B \log N \quad (1)$$

where σ_{\max} , σ_0 denote maximum stress amplitude and static strength, respectively, and A, B are the coefficients of the best fitting line. Apparently, the value of “A” should be perfectly 1, but the intercept of the straight lines generally falls above the static material strength. This inadequacy of Eqs.1 at low lifetimes is usually explained by the hypothesis that the failure modes will change at high stress levels. The results of the best line fitting by Eqn.1 to each series are shown in Table 3 with the static strengths. The average thickness of Cupo1 series was the thinnest and the static strength was extremely low comparing to the other virgin series. The failure mode is supposed to have been different from the others, so it is excluded from subsequent discussion. Observing the values of B in Table 3, they are higher for used series than for virgin ones, except for Cupo1 series. That represents the deterioration of the substance in fatigue strength after long term operation.

Fatigue life time prediction by two-parameter model

Recently, a two-parameter model [5] was proposed, aiming to reduce time and cost for material characterisation and to allow for a reliable evaluation of the probability of failure under assigned operating conditions. The applicability of the model to various types of GFRPs was validated by Caprino et al [6] in four point bending fatigue test at room temperature, and all the experimental results were in good agreement in the paper. It is interesting to validate the applicability of the model to MR laminated plate. The model was based on the hypothesis that the cycle evolution induces a strength decrease according to the following power law:

$$d\sigma_n/dn = -a\sigma_n^{-b} \quad (2)$$

where σ_n is the residual material strength after n cycles. It was assumed that the constant a is linearly dependent on the stress amplitude. $\sigma_N = \sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}$

$$a = a_0 \epsilon^{-b} \quad (3)$$

where a_0 , similarly to b , is a constant for given material and load conditions.

Eqn 3 was substituted in Eqn 2, which was integrated using the boundary condition $n=1$ at $\sigma_N = \sigma_0$, yielding:

$$\sigma_0 - \sigma_N = \langle \epsilon \int_{\sigma_{max}} \epsilon (1-R) \epsilon (n^b - 1) \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 is the static material strength, $R = \sigma_{min} / \sigma_{max}$ the stress ratio, and

$$\langle = a_0 / (1 - b) \quad (5)$$

$$b = 1 - b \quad (6)$$

The critical number of cycles to failure, N , was calculated putting $\sigma_N = \sigma_{max}$ in Eqn 4, i.e., supposing that failure takes place when the residual material strength equals the maximum applied stress. Solving for N , it was obtained:

$$N = \left[\frac{\sigma_0 - \sigma_{max}}{\langle \epsilon (1-R) \epsilon (n^b - 1)} \right]^{1/b}$$

As previously mentioned, two-parameter model was validated by using four point bending fatigue test results, and it was reported that the final collapse was due to the unstable propagation of a single crack, located on the sample surface subjected to tension and approximately perpendicular to the beam longitudinal axis in Ref.6. Supposing from the report, the model is applicable when failure mode is single or regarded as equivalently single to be governed by Eqn 2.

All the present test results were applied to the model, and the results showed good agreement for all tensile loaded series, but compressive and used ones.

Fig.8 Life time prediction for Tipo2,4,6 series by two parameter model

In Table 4, Tupo6 have the higher \textcircled{R} value comparing with that of Tupo2. From the definition in Eqn 2 and 6, the larger \textcircled{R} means the rapider decrease of residual strength, and that leads high fatigue sensitivity, i.e., the shorter life time. The fiber contents of those two series are quite close, but Tupo6 series is thicker than Tupo2 series by 1.7. The comparison result supports the tendency in Fig. 1, i.e., the increase of thickness brings the reduction of life time in high cycles. It is expected that the further detail study on this issue reveals some relation between the constants in the model and fiber content or thickness.

Table 4: The constants in two-parameter model with fiber content, V_f , thickness, and judgement of the applicability of the model for each series

Series	\langle	\textcircled{R}	6Φ [%]	Thickness [mm]	Judgement
Tupo1	0.0275	0.277	36.2	4.26	excellent
Tupo2	0.0696	0.228	33.7	6.88	excellent
Tupo3	0.0932	0.230	35.2	9.23	good
Tupo4	0.113	0.192	28.1	6.23	excellent
Tupo5	0.146	0.173	30.1	9.18	excellent
Tupo6	0.0409	0.284	33.9	11.68	excellent
Cupo1	-	-	36.2	4.5	none
Cupo2	-	-	33.7	6.2	none
Cupo3	0.354	0.108	35.2	9.1	good
CLBL1	0.0152	0.255	27.2	8.5	poor
CLBT2	-	-	31.9	8.7	none

Transition Curves of Secant Modulus

Secant modulus is one of the significant properties for viscoelastic-plastic substance and commonly used to represent the characteristics under cyclic loading. From the definition shown in Fig.9, where \int, Σ denote normal stress amplitude and strain, respectively, it is obvious that the value will decrease as the increase of inner defects. The values were calculated from the both peaks of a load and a deformation, and the hysteresis loops were frequently monitored on the master computer's display during fatigue test. In this section the whole tendencies are discussed from a macroscopic

Fig.10 Transition curve of secant modulus for cupo1 series

Fig.11 Transition curve of secant modulus for cupo2 series

Fig.12 Transition curve of secant modulus for cupo3

Fig.13 Transition curve of secant modulus for CLBL1

Fig.14 Transition curve of secant modulus for CLBT2

Fig.15 Transition curve of secant modulus for Tupo1

Fig.16 Transition curve of secant modulus for Tupo2

Fig.17 Transition curve of secant modulus for Tupo3

view point based on each figure.

Fig.10-12 show the transition curves of secant modulus for each series corresponding to Fig.3-5, and Fig.13,14 are for used series of Fig.6,7. The numbers of cycles are in a logarithmic scale normalized by cycles to failure of each specimen and the ratios to each maximum secant modulus during fatigue test are in a normal scale. The numbers in each parenthesis indicate the values of stress amplitude in the unit of [MPa]. Some features are observed from the figures. First, for the cases which have relatively long

life time, the transition curves have the minimums in their early stages. This means that it took long time for low stress levels to reach stable fatigue stage. Second, the reductions of secant modulus initiate around at ten percent of their life time periods, and the values gradually decrease until they suddenly meet rapid falling off right before breaking off. This phenomenon implies that the final failure mode was buckling. Third, comparing the secant modulus transition curves of used series to those of virgin ones, no initial reduction was observed for used ones. This is supposed that the initial irregularity in the substance had been leveled by substantial wave loads. Finally, there are some different types of curves in each figure, the case for cupo1-16, for example. For those cases, the initial material condition is supposed to have been different from the others, and scatter in S-N plot could be caused by not only scatter on static strength but also the difference on the dominant parameter during fatigue process such as crack propagation, hardening of resin, for example.

Let the compressive virgin series of Fig.10-12 be compared to the tensile series of Fig.15-17. Most of tensile ones have relatively large monotonous reductions in comparison with those of compressive ones, and the figures of the curves are almost similar one another. The tendency suggests that some simple parameter, macro crack propagation for example, governs the fatigue damage accumulating process under tensile cyclic loading. Finally comparing Fig.17-19 one another focused on thickness, it seems that the irregularity of the curves become plainer as the increase of thickness or the number of lamina. That seems to imply the increase of inner defects or decrease of uniformity due to the increase of interfaces between the fibers and the resin, and the laminas. On the contrary, there observed no apparent dispersions in Fig.10-12, which means that the fatigue damage accumulating process for compressive loading is stabler than that for tensile one on the increase of thickness. This tendency supports the result that compressive fatigue strength is superior to tensile one.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, axial tensile and compressive fatigue tests were carried out on virgin and used GFRP laminated plates. The fiber content, thickness were varied as focused parameters and the effects to fatigue life time and the process were discussed from the tendencies in each S-N plot and transition curves of secant modulus. Furthermore, the applicability of two-parameter model to MR laminated plates were discussed. The obtained main points are as follows:

- (1) Fatigue strength of MR laminated plate is governed by fiber content in low cycles, and the influence of increasing in thickness to the strength gradually appears to be an outstanding reduction of stress amplitude as the increase of the cycles to failure.
- (2) The effect of long term operation to the fatigue strength appeared as a notable reduction of stress amplitude in S-N plot, and fatigue sensitivities calculated by Eqn 1 were higher for used series than for virgin ones.
- (3) Two-parameter model is applicable to MR laminated plate under axial cyclic tensile load condition, and the influences of fiber content and thickness were represented by constant θ in the model.

- (4) The transition curve of secant modulus properly represents fatigue damage accumulating process. The shape reflects the dominant process under various loading conditions and material properties during fatigue test.

REFERENCES

1. Kimpara, I., "On the Strength and Stiffness of laminated FRP plates", *Bulletin of Society of Naval Architects of Japan*, Vol. 777, 1994, pp. 180-185.
2. Reifsnider, K.L., *Fatigue of Composite Materials*, Comp Mater Series, Vol. 4, Elsevier, Amsterdam.
3. Suzuki, M., *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan*, Vol. 31, pp.1150-1158.
4. Suzuki, M., *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan*, Vol. 32, pp.82-92.
5. D'Amore, A., Caprino, G., Stupak, J.Zhou and Nicolais, L., "Effect of Stress Ratio on the Flexural Fatigue Behavior of Continuous Strand Mat Reinforced Plastics", *Science and Engineering of Composite Materials*, Vol. 5, No.1, pp. 1-8.
6. Caprino, G., D'Amore, A. and Facciolo, F., "Fatigue Sensitivity of Random glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 32, No.12, 1998, pp.1203-1220.